

RISK OF SUICIDE AMONG THE POPULATION, CAUSES AND TYPES OF INTERVENTIONS: LITERATURE VIEW

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Abstract

Suicide poses a significant public health challenge worldwide, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of its risk factors, underlying causes, and effective interventions. This review examines the multifaceted nature of suicide risk and explores interventions aimed at prevention and support.

Materials and Methods:

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify relevant studies, reviews, and meta-analyses addressing suicide risk factors, causes, and interventions. Electronic databases including PubMed, PsycINFO, and Google Scholar were searched using appropriate keywords. Studies published in English from peer-reviewed journals were included, with a focus on recent publications to capture up-to-date information.

Outcomes:

The review synthesizes findings on the complex interplay of risk factors contributing to suicide, encompassing mental health disorders, social determinants, and demographic variables. Additionally, it examines the underlying causes of suicidal behavior, shedding light on the psychological, social, and environmental factors driving suicide risk.

Clinical Manifestations and Implications:

Clinical manifestations of suicide risk encompass a wide spectrum of behaviors and emotions, ranging from suicidal ideation and self-harm to completed suicide. Mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety, and substance abuse often manifest as key clinical indicators of heightened suicide risk. Social isolation, interpersonal conflicts, and experiences of trauma further contribute to the clinical presentation of suicidal behavior.

Diagnostic Approaches:

Diagnostic approaches to suicide risk involve comprehensive assessment of mental health status, including screening for psychiatric disorders and evaluation of risk factors. Standardized measures such as the Columbia-Suicide Severity Rating Scale (C-SSRS) may be utilized to assess the severity of suicidal ideation and behavior. Additionally, thorough psychosocial assessments help identify underlying stressors and vulnerabilities contributing to suicide risk.

Interventions and Strategies:

Interventions include psychotherapy, medication, crisis intervention services, safety planning, and community support programs. Gatekeeper training, postvention strategies, collaborative care models, and public policy initiatives also play crucial roles. Additionally, resilience-building programs aim to strengthen coping skills and support networks, ultimately reducing suicide risk and promoting mental well-being.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, suicide represents a multifaceted public health issue influenced by a myriad of factors spanning mental health, social, and environmental domains. By elucidating the diverse risk factors, underlying causes, and effective interventions, we can strive towards reducing the incidence of suicide and providing essential support to individuals in crisis. Continued research and investment in suicide prevention efforts are critical for addressing this complex public health challenge.

Keywords: Suicide, Risk factors, depression, suicidal ideation, mental health, anxiety, and substance abuse.

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